

Sleeping Beauties in OpenAlex

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We present the first systematic and comprehensive search for publications with delayed recognition (also called “Sleeping Beauties”, SBs) indexed in the freely available bibliographic database OpenAlex applying the parametric algorithm by van Raan and Winnink (2019) with sleeping times of 10, 20, and 30 years. We find SBs between 1909 and 2008, and compare the time development of the number of SBs with that of the overall number of publications, references, and citation counts in OpenAlex. We calculate a probability of SB occurrence. Moreover, we discuss the SB distribution over the 19 top-level concepts in OpenAlex during these 100 years and find a remarkable prevalence of the concepts from the humanities Art, History, and Philosophy as well as Computer Science.

1. Introduction

The phenomenon of scientific discoveries going unnoticed for a significant number of years before their importance is appreciated had been described since the 1960s and termed delayed recognition in a selective bibliometric study by sociologist Cole (1970). Garfield (1980) took on this subject, gave some examples, asked for possible reasons and suggested quantitative bibliometric methods to detect papers with delayed recognition in the past, by comparing to typical citation patterns of research articles, differing from field to field. Later he discussed five outstanding examples, which had been found by such a citation frequency analysis of highly cited papers Garfield (1989), in this case requiring a low citation frequency of about one per year for the first at least five years (preferably more than ten). Garfield is conscious of the limitations of an algorithmic search for such unusual papers (“...where the expert systems may fail, the human brain may succeed”) and also of their rarity, which Glänzel and Garfield (2004) could quantify—using a certain parametric definition—to about 1 in 10,000 papers in the Web of Science database for the publication year 1980.

In the same year van Raan (2004) had introduced the nick name “Sleeping Beauties” (SB) for papers suffering delayed recognition and presented a parametric method to identify “Sleeping Beauties in science” from bibliographic databases. He applied it to the Web of Science (WoS) (Birkle, Pendlebury, Schnell, et al., 2020) in the form of an in-house custom database at CWTS, Leiden, which only contained the publication years from 1980 onwards and calculated a statistics deriving his “Grand Sleeping Beauty Equation”—a kind of scaling law to predict the prevalence of SBs from the given parameters. 15 years later van Raan and Winnink (2019) focused on SBs in medical research since 1980 and tried to measure their technological impact by the number and distribution of their citations in patents.

Since a systematic search for SBs in the WoS web-interface is not feasible, finding SBs before the year 1980 is rather accidental. The aim of the present study is to go beyond those time and field limitations and to apply the parametric method of van Raan to search for SBs in the whole 20th century and up to the present in a free multidisciplinary bibliographic database and investigate their statistics, especially according to the diverse fields of research. As now with OpenAlex as the successor of Microsoft Academic Graph a totally open bibliographic database is available (Priem, Piwowar, & Orr, 2022), we could easily expand the investigated time periods to a much earlier beginning than in WoS. To the best of our knowledge this is the first comprehensive search for SBs in OpenAlex or its predecessor Microsoft Academic Graph from

which the relevant metadata—at least up to 2020—had nearly completely been taken over (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023).

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Van Raan's Algorithm

The algorithm by van Raan and Winnink (2019) contains four main search parameters: (i) the sleeping time s in years, (ii) a maximum number of citations cs received per year on average during sleep, (iii) the awakening period a in years directly after the sleeping time, and (iv) a minimum number of citations ca received per year on average during awakening. They had iterated through a lot of combinations of these parameters, going up to a maximal s of 30, in this case covering only three publication years in the WoS.

In the present paper, we are mainly interested in expanding the coverage of publication years for the sleeping times van Raan and Winnink (2019) had used in WoS. We fix the average annual citation rate during sleep cs to 1.0 and the awakening period a to 5 years with at least 5.0 citations on average per year ca , amounting to at least 25 citations during the awakening period. These choices are in any case arbitrary.

2.2. OpenAlex data

OurResearch is regularly providing snapshots of the whole OpenAlex database (Priem, et al., 2022). These are regularly ingested into an in-house Postgres database at FIZ Karlsruhe and provided to the members of the German “Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie” (KB, Competence Network for Bibliometrics, <http://www.bibliometrie.info>). In particular, we used the OpenAlex snapshot of August 2023 with more than 237.8 million publication records in the time period from 1800 to 2022 (see the red line in Figure 1). As opposed to other bibliographic databases like WoS or Scopus, there are only linked references and linked citations contained in OpenAlex. Culbert, Hobert, Jahn, et al. (2024) have recently given evidence for the source reference coverage in OpenAlex to be comparable to that in WoS and Scopus when looking at DOIs from the intersection of all three databases with publication years between 2015 and 2022. For the quick inspection of single SB candidates and their citation patterns, the new web interface <https://openalex.org/> launched in January 2024 proved to be a useful tool.

3. Results

3.1. Distribution of SBs over the years

For the three sleeping times $s = 10, 20,$ and 30 years, the earliest SB was published in 1909 ($s=10$). For $s=20$, there is one earlier paper (Miller (1862), OpenAlex ID: W3092028991) formally matching the SB criteria. It had not been cited during the first 20 years but of the 33 total citations 27 occurred in 1883, i.e., 21 years after the publication—and all are assigned to the German textbook Kayser (1883) on spectral analysis and its many chapters going through chemical elements one by one with similar bibliographies, so that we do not count it as a genuine SB. Therefore, we begin with our analyses in the publication year 1900.

Figure 1 is a compact logarithmic presentation of the time development of several annual counts in OpenAlex. For a better comparison of the curves, the annual numbers of publications, linked references, and linked citations are given in thousands. The number of publications more or less displays a monotonous growth, only to be disturbed by significant decrease during the two world wars and by some smaller upward bulges at full decades. The other two counts largely follow the same pattern, but there are two remarkable peaks in the number of linked references

in years 1911 and 1920. Many book chapters from German reference works published by Springer in 1911 have a lot of references. The 46 book chapters alone that contain more than 125 references each (up to 1454) account for 19,784 references, which are about half of all references (38,657) in the year 1911 stemming from a total of 91,310 publications. In the other peak year 1920, four *recent* books with 67 chapters in total published *after 2000* by Cambridge University Press (O'Connor & Muysken, 2014; Sabin P, 2007a, 2007b; Sharwood Smith & Truscott, 2014) are incorrectly assigned to this publication year and account for 24,206 references, i.e., nearly a half of the 54,874 references in the whole year provided by 92,461 items. Furthermore, the reference counts for each chapter seem to be derived from the reference lists at the end of the books.

Requiring two-digit numbers of SBs and starting with the first year this condition is fulfilled for all three sleeping times, we apply a linear regression to all curves from 1951 to 2008 (the last year with SBs). We find slopes (and doubling times in years) for the SB curves with $s = 10$, 20, and 30 of 0.081 (8.5), 0.075 (9.3), and 0.081 (8.5), respectively, i.e., between those of the references with 0.086 (8.1) and the citations with 0.067 (10.3) which could have been expected. Additionally, we calculated average annual growth rates of 12.4%, 8.6%, and 11.4% for $s = 10$, 20, and 30, respectively, as well as 8.6% for the number of references and 5.9% for the number of citations. All three SB curves have similar shapes at their respective ends: About 15 years before the end of the data series, they reach a plateau, then exhibit a significant dip five years before the end of the data series, and finally again exponentially grow to their maximum at the end of the data series with a higher slope than before.

A common feature of all SB curves is a significant dip during World War II. Before the latter, there are some years with single SBs before multiple SBs per year become the norm which warrant a closer inspection in order to verify that the single SBs per year are valid SBs as opposed to Miller (1862) (see above). We were able to verify the single SBs in years 1909, 1912, 1932, and 1935 for $s=10$, in 1910, 1926, and 1930 for $s=20$, and in 1922 and 1926 for $s=30$.

Figure 1: Logarithmic presentation of annual numbers of publications, linked references, and linked citations as well as of SBs with $s = 10, 20,$ and 30 from 1900 to 2022 in OpenAlex.

3.2. Probability of SBs over the years

In order to estimate the probability of SBs, we divide the number of SBs by the number of not awakened papers (NAPs), defined as those papers that have slept for s years and collected less than 25 citations during the next $a = 5$ years—excluding papers not cited at all in the time period $s+a$. Table 1 shows the respective total numbers of SBs and NAPs from 1900 to 1988 where SBs for all three sleeping times could have been published and the ratios indicating the probability of being an SB. There is a high overlap between the resp. NAPs. The probability clearly increases with s .

Table 1. Numbers of SBs and NAPs for $s = 10, 20,$ and 30 in the time period 1900 to 1988 and their ratios as measure of SB occurrence probability. For the NAPs, the overlap, i.e., the number of common documents for $s = 10, 20,$ and $30,$ is given.

s	#SBs	#NAPs	Ratio in per mille
10	4497	11,406,780	0.39
20	5753	11,810,930	0.49
30	6226	12,066,728	0.52
Overlap		11,161,343	

When breaking the data down to annual counts and ratios as in Figure 2, we find some interesting features: (i) extraordinarily high probabilities for $s=30$ and $s=20$ during World War II, (ii) extraordinarily high probabilities for $s=10$ after 1988 with a maximum around 1992, and (iii) a time difference of about ten years, each, between the most recent highest peaks for $s = 10, 20,$ and $30,$ respectively.

Figure 2: Annual SB probabilities for $s = 10, 20,$ and $30,$ given in per mille, since 1900. Horizontal lines indicate the aggregated values from Table 1 for the years from 1900 to 1988.

3.3. Distribution of SBs over the top-level concepts

OpenAlex has a hierarchical classification scheme according to the so called concepts ("*Fields of Study*" in MAG) with 19 top-level concepts. All SBs are assigned to at least one top-level concept. Note that some publications are assigned to multiple top-level concepts.

Table 2 shows the distribution of all SBs from Table 1 for each s according to their top-level concepts. Due to multiple assignments of papers to concepts the numbers in Table 2 add up to more than the numbers given in Table 1. Contrary to Table 1, the highest numbers occur always for $s=20$ which is correlated with a nearly twice as large average number of top-level concepts assigned to each SB. In order to give a plausible ranking, we sum up the numbers for all three sleeping times. Table 3 lists the corresponding numbers of NAPs. Finally, Table 4 combines the value of tables 2 and 3, displaying the probabilities for being an SB for $s=10, 20,$ or $30,$ given as the ratio of the number of SBs to the number of NAPs.

We have highlighted three small groups of concepts that are displaying three noticeable and different profiles in tables 2 to 4 and use different font colors for them. Remarkably, the only three top-level concepts that belong to the Humanities (**Art, History, and Philosophy**) lie within the top five ranks in Table 2. That they rank lowly in Table 3 lets them occupy even the highest three ranks in Table 4. The second group is made up of the concepts **Medicine, Chemistry, and Biology**. They are placed closely together on the middle ranks 9 to 11 in Table 2, while holding the top three positions in Table 3 puts them among the last four ranks in Table 4. **Physics** and

Computer Science in the third group show a different profile: They rank similarly very high in Table 2 but also in Table 3 so that they both end up mid-range in Table 4.

Table 2. Distribution of SBs across the top-level concepts for $s = 10, 20,$ and 30 in the time period 1900 to 1988, ranked according to the total number of SBs. Three groups of concepts discussed above are marked by different font colors.

Concept	#SB for $s=10$	#SB for $s=20$	#SB for $s=30$	Sum
Philosophy	1187	2695	1589	5471
Computer science	1069	2598	1573	5240
History	1193	2267	1360	4820
Physics	875	2070	1438	4383
Art	944	1857	1139	3940
Political science	783	1951	1054	3788
Mathematics	707	1726	1173	3606
Psychology	881	1298	688	2867
Biology	652	1264	777	2693
Medicine	738	1166	672	2576
Chemistry	488	1166	757	2411
Sociology	403	1161	636	2200
Materials science	261	885	620	1766
Economics	346	891	526	1763
Engineering	263	877	560	1700
Geography	370	746	488	1604
Geology	220	564	361	1145
Business	129	422	212	763
Environmental science	64	275	196	535
Sum	11,573	25,879	15,819	-
<i>Avg. number of top-level concepts per SB</i>	2.57	4.50	2.54	

Table 3. Distribution of NAPs across the top-level concepts for $s = 10, 20,$ and 30 in the time period 1900 to 1988. The ranking is the same for each s . Three groups of concepts discussed above are marked by different font colors.

Concept	#NAPs for $s=10$	#NAPs for $s=20$	#NAPs for $s=30$
Medicine	3,438,687	3,575,304	3,673,640
Chemistry	2,890,370	3,095,231	3,227,179
Biology	2,761,034	2,930,461	3,046,946
Physics	2,446,381	2,582,130	2,657,740
Computer science	2,371,345	2,431,404	2,465,335
Mathematics	1,509,107	1,551,147	1,571,158

Materials science	1,267,703	1,329,914	1,363,575
Philosophy	1,159,583	1,171,381	1,176,278
Psychology	1,089,959	1,108,893	1,124,454
Engineering	1,085,042	1,105,588	1,115,433
Political science	947,026	949,259	949,317
Geography	764,792	765,798	765,786
Geology	712,564	726,988	734,786
Art	633,275	633,500	633,374
History	595,840	594,210	593,362
Economics	572,594	580,878	584,849
Sociology	562,456	564,573	565,917
Environmental science	475,747	481,438	484,342
Business	369,015	370,015	369,606

Table 4. Distribution of SB probabilities in per mille across the top-level concepts for $s = 10$, 20, and 30 in the time period 1900 to 1988, ranked according to the respective sums that otherwise have no significance. Three groups of concepts discussed above are marked by different font colors.

Concept	#SBs/#NAPs for $s=10$	#SBs/#NAPs for $s=20$	#SBs/#NAPs for $s=30$	Sum
History	1.27	1.36	1.40	4.03
Art	0.86	0.98	1.09	2.94
Philosophy	0.64	0.70	0.75	2.10
Political science	0.51	0.52	0.61	1.64
Sociology	0.46	0.50	0.51	1.47
Economics	0.41	0.35	0.51	1.27
Psychology	0.42	0.36	0.37	1.16
Mathematics	0.32	0.33	0.37	1.01
Geography	0.35	0.33	0.34	1.01
Computer science	0.32	0.30	0.34	0.96
Business	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.79
Physics	0.26	0.25	0.27	0.78
Geology	0.22	0.24	0.21	0.66
Engineering	0.20	0.17	0.23	0.60
Materials science	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.50
Biology	0.18	0.13	0.12	0.44
Environmental science	0.16	0.13	0.14	0.43
Chemistry	0.17	0.14	0.11	0.41
Medicine	0.15	0.12	0.11	0.38

3.4. Distribution of SBs over the top-level concepts and the years

Figure 3 shows the annual numbers of SBs aggregated over all three sleeping times and split across the top-level concepts. Two dotted vertical lines distinguish three time periods: (i) the time before the local minimum just after the end of World War II containing the very first, but relatively few SBs; (ii) the rest of the time span evaluated in Tables 2 to 4; and (iii) the years beyond which contain only SBs for $s=20$ (until 1998) and $s=10$ (until 2008). The concepts are grouped into the following broad subject fields that are marked by a specific point shape: humanities (Hum): Art, History, and Philosophy; bio-medical sciences (BM): Biology, Medicine, Psychology, Environmental Science; social sciences (Soc): Business, Economics, Political Science, Sociology; applied sciences (Apl): Engineering, Geography, Computer Science, Geology; chemical-physical-technical sciences (CPT): Physics, Chemistry, Materials Science, Mathematics.

In the first period, we are now going to have a look at the concepts of the earliest *single* SBs for the three different sleeping times:

- **$s=10$:** The very first SB is Henderson (1909) on “The balance between bases and acids in the animal organism” which is only assigned to Chemistry, but being published in the *Journal of Physiology, Medicine or Biology* would also be a good choice. Similarly, “About the function of the pituitary gland” by Aschner (1912) is only assigned to Biology but is also related to Medicine. The “Studies in the biochemistry of micro-organisms” by Clutterbuck, Lovell, and Raistrick (1932) are correctly assigned to Biology and Chemistry as well as “the Formation of Agglutinins Within Lymph Nodes” by McMaster and Hudack (1935) to Biology and Medicine. So the earliest SBs for $s=10$ are all from Medicine.
- **$s=20$:** The definitely medicinal paper Padtberg (1910) “on the importance of the skin as a chlorine depot” is mysteriously assigned to Philosophy and Art, but Mitchell and Carman (1926) on the “biological value of ... animal food” with its table of calculations suites well to the assigned concepts Chemistry, Mathematics, and Biology. The work of Nobel prize winner Dirac (1930) on the approximate calculation of atomic states is correctly assigned to Physics and Mathematics, but the third concept Computer science might be due to the term “calculation” in the title.
- **$s=30$:** The work on “The Chemistry of Muscular Contraction” from 1922 is only a note, not a research article, and probably mistaken by OpenAlex for the book by Szent-Györgyi (1947) with nearly the same title to which all citations (starting only in 1948) refer. So the first true SB is Kronig (1926) on quantum theoretical calculations which is appropriately assigned to Physics and additionally to Computer science like Dirac (1930).

Judging from Figure 2 and Figure 3, the peak in 1935 is mainly caused by SBs for $s=30$ which are predominantly assigned to Medicine ($n=8$), Philosophy ($n=5$), and Computer Science ($n=3$). In contrast, the even higher numbers during World War II are mainly due to papers in History: The associated SBs for $s=30$ have the highest numbers in the years 1940 ($n=6$), 1941 ($n=23$), 1942 ($n=14$), and 1943 ($n=11$).

The second period contains the bulk of SBs and therefore, the top curves reflect the rankings in Table 2 and show an exponential growth similar to Figure 1.

In the last period after 1988, there is no exponential growth anymore, but the numbers and rankings across the concepts are more or less the same in 1988 and 2008 with the shape in

between reflecting the overall picture described for Figure 1 above, especially the dips at 1993 and 2003, and the steep growth during the last five years.

Figure 3: Annual total number of SBs for $s = 10, 20,$ and 30 together across the top-level concepts in the time period 1900 to 2008. The interested reader can zoom into the plot via an online version under the URL <https://s.gwdg.de/PxsyFk>.

4. Discussion

We applied the methodology of van Raan and Winnink (2019) for the first time to the whole 20th century and to the freely available bibliographic database OpenAlex in order to identify SBs with sleeping times of 10, 20, or 30 years published even long before 1980, the time limit of previous analyses mainly using WoS. We were able to find the earliest “true” SB in 1909 thereby spanning a whole century of SBs until the last possible year 2008. The time development of SBs is much aligned to that of the numbers of publications, references and citations inside the database. The probability of papers becoming SBs also increases on average over time, but shows a remarkable peak at the beginning of World War II. After analysing the SB data according to the 19 top-level concepts of OpenAlex we identified History as the main contributor to that peak starting the prevalence of the humanities during the remaining years. Examining the very first SBs, we only found a few questionable concept assignments. The very first SBs with a sleeping time of 10 years are definitely from Medicine, but the early occurrences of Computer Science as well as its prevalence from World War II onwards warrant some further scrutiny.

As limitations of our work, we at first address the limitations of the underlying database: OpenAlex has a broad but by no means complete coverage of the scientific literature and it has errors in the identification of publications and their citation relations which – due to thresholds in the method– may lead to false positives and also false negatives in the search for NAPs and SBs. The definitely occurring wrong assignments to top-level concepts in OpenAlex could

distort the corresponding results especially in earlier years with relatively few SBs. The algorithm of van Raan and Winnink (2019) itself is sensitive to small changes in the parameter values. By introducing a deliberate uncertainty, there would probably be found more SBs. This leads us to possible further studies that use other of the few SB search algorithms that have been proposed in the literature.

Open science practices

The data of OpenAlex are freely available for all purposes (especially the data dumps called snapshots, see <https://docs.openalex.org/download-all-data/openalex-snapshot>). The software for evaluation and visualization is based on the open source language R (R_Core_Team, 2022), in particular the R package *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016), and can be provided on request.

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Author contributions

T.S.: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Visualization, Writing– original draft, Writing – review & editing

R.H.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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